

Global COSMOS Reference

*A community reference
for the processing of sensor data of the
COsmic-ray Soil Moisture Observing System*

Version 0.9.2

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Preface

Over the last 15 years, the COsmic-ray Soil Moisture Observing System (COSMOS) based on Cosmic-Ray Neutron Sensing technology (CRNS) has undergone tremendous development. The knowledge of the methodology, particularly the underlying physical principles and the environmental factors affecting its signal, has advanced immensely. The potential and limitations of CRNS for hydrological applications are much better understood today than they were a few years ago.

However, enormous scientific progress comes at a cost. With the manifold of additional findings that accumulated over the last years, it is more and more difficult to gain an adequate overview of the current state of knowledge, especially for new users. This creates new challenges for further dissemination of the measurement method.

At the same time, there are increased efforts to further advance the standardization of environmental observations globally. Data processing standards are being developed in this context. Nevertheless, there is presently no available standard for the processing of CRNS data that is coordinated within the international CRNS community. Against this background, CRNS scientists have joined forces to develop a reference guideline for the processing of CRNS data.

The reference is defined as a comprehensive compilation of concepts for CRNS data processing that reflect an established status of knowledge that has been successfully and adequately applied in recent years by the CRNS community. ***It is crucial to emphasize at this point that the present reference should neither be interpreted as an exclusionary benchmark, nor as the only possible way to process CRNS data.*** Instead, it is to be seen as a scientific basis which individual processing approaches could build upon, and which future research can be compared against.

In that sense, the reference document...

1. can serve as a basis for current and future activities of international harmonization of CRNS-base observation of soil moisture,
2. provides immediately available and clear guidance for new users for the implementation of the CRNS method,
3. can be used as a standardized benchmark to test and proof new concepts against as well as allowing for easy reproducibility of experiments.

Consequently, the COSMOS reference is a living document that can be continuously developed in joint consultation. We encourage the community to continuously review and develop the state of knowledge described in this version.

Release notes for version 0.9.2

This is a preliminary draft.

Glossary

COSMOS	COsmic-ray Soil moisture Observing System
CRNS	Cosmic-Ray Neutron Sensing
HDPE	High-density polyethylene
NMDB	Neutron Monitor Database
UTC	Coordinated universal time

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1 Introduction

Measured epithermal neutrons are a proxy for soil water content, but systematic factors and stochastic effects also influence the neutron signal. Research in the last decades has led to a profound understanding of these influencing factors and has facilitated a more accurate extraction of the soil moisture signal from the cosmic-ray neutron data. The commonly agreed processing framework is described below, following the scheme visualized in Fig. 1. Its technical implementation can be supported by public tools and software libraries, such as Corny, Crspy, or Nepton.

⚠ This document applies to moderated neutron detectors. They are usually shielded by 20-25 mm of polyethylene to become most sensitive to epithermal neutrons. The processing routines for bare thermal neutron detectors or leaded high-energy neutron detectors may vary.

Figure 1: General scheme for COSMOS data processing with the main processing steps (lightgrey), subtasks (white), optional steps (dashed), and dependencies on external data sources (grey).

2 Sensor placement

In order to reduce the systematic uncertainties due to landscape features, it is recommended that the COSMOS station is installed at a height of 1.5-2 m above the ground. Also, the ideal surrounding landscape should be rather homogeneous and have a flat topography, a single or a dominant land use (i.e., not partly irrigated), no artificial features (i.e., buildings, high voltage power lines), and no water bodies within 100 m distance.

3 Raw data requirements

The minimum requirements for raw data from COSMOS measurements include the following columns:

Variable	Units	Symbol
Date and time, ideally synchronized	UTC	t
Epithermal neutron count rate	counts per period or elapsed time	N_{raw}

Data that is required for the processing, but could be taken from another source:

Variable	Units	Symbol
Air pressure	hPa or mbar	P
Air temperature	°C	T
Air relative humidity	%	h_{rel}

Optional data that is helpful for the processing and sensor diagnostics:

Variable	Units	Symbol
Elapsed time since the last record	sec	Δt
Battery voltage	V	U
Internal air temperature	°C	T_{int}
Internal air humidity	%	$h_{\text{int,rel}}$
Redundant air pressure sensors	hPa or mbar	P_i

4 Cleaning raw data

Raw data can be inconsistent due to several reasons (transmission signal loss, power cuts, restarts). Typically, a cleaning process is necessary to provide a consistent data stream. This process involves the following steps:

1. Drop lines with inconsistent number of columns,
2. Drop lines with missing or duplicated datetime values,
3. Drop first hour of data after starting or restarting the CRNS device, as this record may have an uncertain integration period,
4. Replace non-numeric values by NaN,
5. Sort data by datetime.

5 General quality control

Suspicious or unrealistic data values should be replaced by NaN or dropped. The following ranges are recommended for filtering:

Variable	Minimum value	Maximum value
t	installation date	future values
N_{raw}	0	individual
P	500	1100
T	-50	50
h_{rel}	0	100
$h_{\text{int,rel}}$	0	80
U	10.5	20

6 Uncertainty determination

Counting neutrons is a random process. In periods of no external influences, their values follow a Poisson distribution with a well defined standard deviation,

$$\sigma_{N_{\text{raw}}} = \sqrt{N_{\text{raw}}}. \quad (1)$$

This value represents the uncertainty, or stochastic error of a neutron measurement. It is useful for further quality control and processing, and for the calculation of the final soil moisture error.

! Since the theory behind this calculation is based on the counting process itself, this step must be performed on the *raw* neutron counts and *before* any unit conversion or correction.

7 Neutron count harmonization

Harmonized neutron count rates, N , should be in units of counts per hour (cph) to facilitate easy intercomparison between CRNS sites. This requires a conversion factor, u , on the raw neutron counts. The same unit conversion needs to be applied on the raw uncertainty:

$$N = N_{\text{raw}} \cdot u, \quad \sigma_N = \sigma_{N_{\text{raw}}} \cdot u. \quad (2)$$

Units of N_{raw}	Conversion factor u
counts per hour (cph)	1
counts per second (cps)	3600
counts per elapsed time Δt (in sec)	$\Delta t/3600$

If not explicitly provided as a column, the elapsed time Δt is the time difference between records.

8 Neutron corrections

The amount of epithermal neutrons in the environment is subject to change, even in periods of constant soil moisture. Therefore, corrections need to be applied to remove variations of neutron counts that are not related to soil moisture changes. It is recommended to address the four most important influencing factors - (i) atmospheric pressure, (ii) air humidity, (iii) incoming neutron intensity, (iv) biomass water - by introducing four correction factors, C , that act multiplicative on the neutron count rate, N , to provide the corrected neutron count rate, N' :

$$N' = N \cdot C_p \cdot C_h \cdot C_{\text{inc}} \cdot C_{\text{veg}}. \quad (3)$$

The same correction factors need to be applied on the uncertainty, σ_N :

$$\sigma_{N'} = \sigma_N \cdot C_p \cdot C_h \cdot C_{\text{inc}} \cdot C_{\text{veg}}. \quad (4)$$

These corrections need to be performed on each neutron measurement, i.e., each time step t , before any further smoothing or aggregation.

8.1 Atmospheric pressure correction

Since the cosmic-ray flux through the atmosphere is attenuated by the traversed cumulative mass, measured neutron count rates can be normalized to standard atmospheric pressure following [Desilets and Zreda, 2003]:

$$C_p = e^{\beta(P - P_{\text{ref}})}, \quad (5)$$

where C_p is atmospheric pressure correction factor, $P_{\text{ref}} = 1013.25$ hPa is the reference atmospheric pressure, P is the measured atmospheric pressure (hPa), and β is the barometric coefficient that is related to the local mass attenuation length of neutrons in air.

It is recommended to calculate β following [Tirado-Bueno et al., 2021]:

$$\beta = 0.0074 - 0.0001 \ln R_c, \quad (6)$$

where $R_c > 0$ is the cut-off rigidity at the site's location, which is described in further detail in section 8.3.

8.2 Air humidity correction

It is currently recommended to correct for the effect of atmospheric water vapour on neutron count rates using the approach of [Rosolem et al., 2013]:

$$C_h = 1 + \alpha (h - h_{\text{ref}}), \quad (7)$$

with $\alpha = 0.0054 \text{ m}^3/\text{g}$, $h_{\text{ref}} = 0 \text{ g/m}^3$ is a reference value, and h is the absolute humidity (g/m^3) measured between 1 and 3 m height. It can be calculated using the established formula:

$$h(h_{\text{rel}}, T) = \frac{6.112 \cdot e^{\frac{17.67 \cdot T}{243.5 + T}}}{273.15 + T} \cdot 2.1674 \cdot h_{\text{rel}}. \quad (8)$$

8.3 Incoming neutron correction

In order to correct data from cosmic-ray neutron sensors (CRNS) for variations of incoming cosmic rays, a general approach is recommended following [Hawdon et al., 2014] and [Schrön et al., 2016]. It is rescaling the CRNS signal using data from a neutron monitor (NM), M , normalised by a reference value, M_{ref} :

$$C_{\text{inc}} = \left[\tau \left(\frac{M}{M_{\text{ref}}} - 1 \right) + 1 \right]^{-1}. \quad (9)$$

Data from neutron monitors, M , can be downloaded from *NMDB*, <https://www.nmdb.eu/nest/>. Make sure that you download pressure- and efficiency-corrected data with absolute count rates. The most reliable record period at NMDB is 1 hour and should generally be smaller or equal to the time resolution of the CRNS data. No general recommendation can be given for the selection of the neutron monitor. It is important, however, to select a nearby NM station, with at least latitude and elevation similar to the CRNS site, and with a complete and revised (error-free) time series. The time resolution should be similar to the original time resolution of the CRNS data and could be interpolated to match the CRNS time stamps. Note that NMDB provides count rates, $M(t)$, for the period between t and $t + \Delta t$, while CRNS sensors usually provide count rates, $N(t)$, for the period between $t - \Delta t$ and t . The variable M_{ref} should be the count rate of the selected NM at a fixed time. It is recommended to use the same value for all COSMOS stations worldwide to facilitate harmonized datasets. This value is currently recommended to be the average value of the period 15th to 22th of March, 2020, given for each NM in Tab. 1. The selected period is situated during a solar minimum, which leads to high neutron count rates due to low solar modulation, providing a defined and stable reference point. The likelihood of large, anisotropic solar events is also greatly reduced during a solar minima.

The scaling factor τ rescales the amplitude of the NMs data by accounting for the different cosmic-ray shielding at different places on Earth. It is recommended to use the recently established approach by [McJannet and Desilets, 2023] to calculate τ by considering the different shielding of cosmic rays on different places on Earth. The difference in shielding depends on the geomagnetic cut-off rigidity,

Station	Data Source	Latitude	Longitude	Elevation	Cut-off rigidity	M_{ref} (cps)
Alma-Ata B	NMDB - 1h	43.14°	76.60°	3340 m	5.2 GV	1434
Inuvik	IZMIRAN	68.36°	-133.72°	21 m	0.1 GV	203
Jungfraujoch IGY	NMDB - 1h	46.55°	7.98°	3570 m	5.0 GV	168
Kerguelen	NMDB	-49.35°	70.25°	33 m	1.0 GV	239
Kiel	NMDB - 1h	54.34°	10.12°	54 m	2.4 GV	190
Lomnický Štit	Station Website	49.20°	20.22°	2634 m	3.4 GV	504
Moscow	IZMIRAN	55.47°	37.32°	200 m	2.2 GV	163
Newark	NMDB - 1h	39.68°	-75.75°	50 m	2.6 GV	100
Novosibirsk	IZMIRAN	54.48°	83.00°	163 m	2.3 GV	198
Oulu	Station Website	65.05°	25.47°	15 m	0.7 GV	113
Terre Adelie	NMDB - 1h	-66.65°	140.00°	32 m	0.0 GV	124
Thule	NMDB - 1h	76.50°	-68.70°	26 m	0.0 GV	130

Table 1: Recommended neutron monitor stations that are stable, reliable, accessible, and operational based on [Väisänen et al., 2021].

R (in GV), and the local atmospheric depth x (in g/cm^2), which can be calculated using the local atmospheric reference pressure, P_{loc} and the local gravitational acceleration, g_{loc} :

$$x = P_{\text{loc}}/g_{\text{loc}}, \quad (10)$$

$$g_{\text{loc}} = c_1 + c_2 \sin^2(\phi) - c_3 \sin^2(2\phi) + (c_4 + c_5 \rho_{\text{rock}}) z, \quad (11)$$

$$P_{\text{loc}} = c_6 (1 + c_7 z)^{c_8 g} \quad (12)$$

where $\rho_{\text{rock}} = 2670 \text{ kg}/\text{m}^3$, $\phi = \text{lat} \cdot \pi/180^\circ$ is the angle in radians using latitude in decimal degrees, and $c_1 = 9.780327$, $c_2 = 0.0518592$, $c_3 = 0.0000567$, $c_4 = -3.086 \cdot 10^{-6}$, $c_5 = 4.194 \cdot 10^{-10}$, $c_6 = 10.1325$, $c_7 = -0.00002256$, $c_8 = 0.5359502$. Using this atmospheric depth, the final correction parameter τ can then be calculated according to [McJannet and Desilets, 2023]:

$$\tau = \epsilon \cdot \frac{1 - c_1 x_N}{1 - c_1 x_M} \cdot \frac{1 - \exp\left(- (c_2 x_N + c_3) R_N^{c_4 x_N - c_5}\right)}{1 - \exp\left(- (c_2 x_M + c_3) R_M^{c_4 x_M - c_5}\right)}, \quad (13)$$

with $c_1 = 0.0005085$, $c_2 = 0.0064$, $c_3 = 1.8855$, $c_4 = 1.3 \cdot 10^{-5}$, $c_5 = 1.2237$. Note that Eq. (13) is not identical, but mathematically equivalent, to the definition given by [McJannet and Desilets, 2023]. The parameters c_0 and c_1 in [McJannet and Desilets, 2023] are reduced to a single parameter c_1 in Eq. (13). The coefficient ϵ is optional and accounts for spectral differences of NMs and CRNS probes, currently assumed to be 1. R_N is the cut-off rigidity of the CRNS site, and R_M is the cut-off rigidity of the neutron monitor. The cutoff-rigidity values for an undisturbed geomagnetic field in year 2020 were calculated by [Gerontidou et al., 2021] and can be obtained from Tab. 2. The cut-off rigidity is subject to change over time. Grids such as the one shown in Tab. 2 have been published in five year intervals, as the changes are not very rapid.

⚠ If nonetheless the effective cut-off rigidity on a specific date is desired it can be calculated using an online tool: <https://tools.izmiran.ru/cutoff>. It is also possible to integrate the calculation of cut-off rigidity into a python workflow using OTSopy package: <https://github.com/NLarsen15/OTSopy>.

Table 2: Cutoff-rigidity, R (in GV), as a function of latitude (rows) and longitude (columns). The data is available from [Gerontidou et al., 2021].

Lat\Lon	-180°	-165°	-150°	-135°	-120°	-105°	-90°	-75°	-60°	-45°	-30°	-15°	0°	15°	30°	45°	60°	75°	90°	105°	120°	135°	150°	165°	180°	
90°	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
85°	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
80°	0.03	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.05	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.05	0.05	0.03
75°	0.13	0.10	0.06	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.04	0.07	0.09	0.11	0.13	0.14	0.15	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.17	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.16	0.13
70°	0.36	0.28	0.19	0.11	0.06	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.05	0.09	0.14	0.20	0.26	0.30	0.33	0.35	0.35	0.36	0.38	0.40	0.42	0.45	0.45	0.42	0.36	
65°	0.79	0.62	0.45	0.29	0.18	0.12	0.09	0.11	0.16	0.25	0.36	0.49	0.59	0.65	0.69	0.71	0.72	0.73	0.76	0.79	0.86	0.91	0.93	0.90	0.79	
60°	1.49	1.21	0.91	0.62	0.41	0.28	0.24	0.26	0.37	0.55	0.78	0.98	1.15	1.26	1.29	1.31	1.33	1.34	1.38	1.44	1.59	1.69	1.75	1.68	1.49	
55°	2.54	2.10	1.62	1.16	0.81	0.58	0.50	0.54	0.76	1.09	1.53	1.87	2.07	2.14	2.17	2.18	2.20	2.24	2.29	2.44	2.65	2.84	2.95	2.84	2.54	
50°	3.93	3.22	2.63	2.01	1.43	1.07	0.92	1.01	1.37	1.98	2.65	3.08	3.33	3.43	3.40	3.40	3.42	3.52	3.62	3.81	4.15	4.38	4.56	4.36	3.93	
45°	5.30	4.66	3.97	3.08	2.33	1.77	1.52	1.70	2.29	3.21	4.22	4.76	4.97	5.02	4.99	4.97	5.10	5.20	5.35	5.56	5.85	6.13	6.21	5.83	5.30	
40°	7.42	6.20	5.29	4.49	3.48	2.72	2.36	2.60	3.59	4.84	5.94	6.91	7.25	7.17	6.95	6.91	7.10	7.35	7.59	7.95	8.62	9.09	9.04	8.49	7.42	
35°	9.32	8.65	7.33	5.81	4.84	3.83	3.41	3.72	4.97	6.94	9.08	9.75	9.80	9.67	9.67	9.88	10.30	10.58	10.83	10.95	11.06	11.34	10.99	10.17	9.32	
30°	11.42	10.19	9.28	8.17	6.42	5.13	4.41	4.96	7.06	9.81	11.00	11.56	11.72	11.71	11.73	12.01	12.44	12.74	13.16	13.65	13.73	13.59	13.13	12.42	11.42	
25°	12.70	11.97	11.18	10.19	8.73	7.00	5.99	6.77	9.31	11.55	12.56	13.14	13.46	13.65	13.83	14.13	14.55	14.95	15.20	15.24	15.11	14.77	14.19	13.47	12.70	
20°	13.56	12.90	12.24	11.45	10.11	8.02	6.65	7.79	11.22	12.56	13.40	13.96	14.36	14.66	14.91	15.25	15.74	16.19	16.43	16.38	16.12	15.65	14.99	14.27	13.56	
15°	14.23	13.64	13.07	12.41	11.39	9.95	9.31	10.50	12.13	13.12	13.81	14.33	14.77	15.15	15.51	15.96	16.52	17.01	17.24	17.14	16.78	16.23	15.56	14.87	14.23	
10°	14.73	14.21	13.70	13.15	12.40	11.49	11.00	11.73	12.61	13.35	13.86	14.29	14.75	15.21	15.67	16.24	16.89	17.42	17.66	17.53	17.11	16.53	15.89	15.29	14.73	
5°	15.04	14.58	14.12	13.64	13.08	12.42	12.04	12.25	12.80	13.29	13.58	13.89	14.33	14.84	15.42	16.11	16.84	17.42	17.67	17.54	17.12	16.55	15.99	15.50	15.04	
0°	15.12	14.74	14.33	13.90	13.43	12.91	12.48	12.45	12.76	12.98	13.02	13.17	13.56	14.10	14.78	15.60	16.40	17.01	17.28	17.19	16.79	16.28	15.82	15.46	15.12	
-5°	14.93	14.66	14.32	13.94	13.53	13.06	12.61	12.44	12.52	12.47	12.24	12.21	12.52	13.06	13.83	14.74	15.59	16.20	16.50	16.45	16.12	15.68	15.34	15.14	14.93	
-10°	14.45	14.30	14.07	13.78	13.43	13.00	12.55	12.25	12.10	11.79	11.27	11.03	11.25	11.82	12.63	13.59	14.43	15.01	15.31	15.33	15.07	14.71	14.50	14.47	14.45	
-15°	13.60	13.65	13.58	13.41	13.14	12.77	12.31	11.90	11.55	10.97	10.14	9.59	9.80	10.31	11.19	12.11	12.87	13.42	13.69	13.78	13.58	13.30	13.25	13.38	13.60	
-20°	12.27	12.66	12.82	12.82	12.66	12.37	11.92	11.40	10.82	9.92	8.86	8.11	8.06	8.60	9.35	10.10	10.64	11.02	11.34	11.49	11.04	10.50	10.58	11.61	12.27	
-25°	9.63	10.67	11.58	12.00	12.01	11.82	11.41	10.74	9.94	8.83	7.58	6.72	6.66	7.11	7.70	8.17	8.31	8.12	8.02	8.11	8.02	7.94	8.46	9.26	9.63	
-30°	7.63	8.99	8.75	10.52	11.16	11.13	10.73	9.96	9.02	7.70	6.35	5.68	5.35	5.55	5.84	5.87	5.69	5.51	5.44	5.41	5.45	5.50	5.83	6.46	7.63	
-35°	5.39	6.27	7.69	7.95	9.68	10.28	9.87	9.13	7.96	6.52	5.56	4.73	4.26	4.20	4.28	4.30	4.14	3.90	3.62	3.57	3.59	3.73	4.17	4.82	5.39	
-40°	3.99	4.49	5.34	6.51	7.85	9.14	8.88	8.12	6.87	5.88	4.75	3.86	3.45	3.34	3.35	3.24	3.01	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.21	3.99	
-45°	3.00	3.25	4.09	4.76	5.86	7.43	7.88	7.34	6.41	5.01	3.88	3.20	2.78	2.63	2.44	2.24	2.04	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.07	3.00	
-50°	2.00	2.18	3.03	3.67	4.42	5.13	5.90	5.76	4.90	3.99	3.21	2.65	2.23	2.05	1.80	1.52	1.21	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.15	2.00	
-55°	1.00	1.32	2.03	3.00	3.25	3.92	4.31	4.27	3.86	3.24	2.65	2.14	1.81	1.53	1.29	1.05	0.75	0.51	0.33	0.25	0.23	0.27	0.38	0.59	1.00	
-60°	0.48	0.77	1.14	2.00	2.17	3.00	3.17	3.32	3.07	2.48	2.04	1.65	1.36	1.13	0.90	0.68	0.45	0.27	0.15	0.09	0.07	0.09	0.15	0.27	0.48	
-65°	0.23	0.42	0.68	1.02	1.40	2.00	2.09	2.23	2.13	1.80	1.50	1.22	1.00	0.80	0.61	0.42	0.26	0.13	0.06	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.11	0.23	
-70°	0.10	0.21	0.37	0.59	0.83	1.07	1.28	1.37	1.34	1.23	1.04	0.88	0.70	0.55	0.40	0.26	0.15	0.06	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.10	
-75°	0.05	0.11	0.20	0.33	0.47	0.62	0.73	0.81	0.81	0.75	0.67	0.57	0.45	0.35	0.25	0.16	0.08	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.05	
-80°	0.03	0.07	0.12	0.18	0.25	0.32	0.38	0.42	0.44	0.42	0.38	0.33	0.27	0.21	0.15	0.10	0.06	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03	
-85°	0.04	0.06	0.08	0.10	0.13	0.16	0.18	0.19	0.20	0.20	0.19	0.17	0.15	0.12	0.10	0.07	0.05	0.04	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.04	
-90°	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.08	0.08	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.08	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.07	

8.4 Biomass correction

Biomass can affect neutron count rates and could be considered when large temporal changes in biomass ($> 1 \text{ kg/m}^2$ per year) occur near the CRNS station. Constant biomass in the footprint is typically not an issue, since the bias would be intrinsically included in the calibration parameters. Correction of dynamic biomass changes is of secondary importance, but could be considered if accurate biomass data is available and the low uncertainty of neutron counts justifies it.

Two currently accepted approaches for biomass correction are based on empirical data from forests [Baatz et al., 2015] or corn and soybean fields [Morris et al., 2024]. They describe the reduction of neutron counts with increasing average dry aboveground biomass, B (in kg/m^2) in the CRNS footprint:

$$C_{\text{veg}} = (1 - \nu B)^{-1}, \quad (14)$$

where $\nu \approx 0.009$ in forests [Baatz et al., 2015] and $\nu \approx 0.020$ in crop fields [Morris et al., 2024]. When B is given as biomass water equivalent, this parameter ν needs to be reduced by half.

8.5 Mobile roving corrections

Mobile cosmic-ray neutron detectors will be considered for future versions of this document.

9 Quality control of processed neutrons

Neutron count rates (in cph) typically vary between a minimum value N'_{min} (fully saturated soil, or ponding water/snow) and a maximum value N'_{max} (completely dry), which are specific for the individual sites and detectors. Once these values were determined experimentally, they could be used in the processing to further flag unrealistic data.

The minimum and maximum values could also be estimated from the free calibration parameter, N_0 , once it has been determined by field calibration (section 15). The exact values can be derived from the neutron-to-soil moisture relationship, described in Eq. (19). This version of the COSMOS standard recommends the use of the relationship presented by [Desilets et al., 2010], where N' cannot be lower than $0.372 N_0$ and not higher than $1.075 N_0$.

In addition, it is unlikely that one neutron measurement deviates much from the previous neutron measurement due to its nearly Gaussian distribution. This characteristics can be used to identify outliers. It is currently recommended to treat every measurement $N'(t_i)$ as an outlier, which deviates more than 20% from the previous measurement, $N'(t_{i-1})$. This may be not applicable during sudden, strong events, such as storm rainfall.

The following table summarizes the above mentioned for recommendations outlier identification.

Variable	Minimum value	Maximum value
N'	N'_{min}	N'_{max}
N'	$0.372 N_0$	$1.075 N_0$
$N'(t_i)$	$0.8 \cdot N'(t_{i-1})$	$1.2 \cdot N'(t_{i-1})$

10 Temporal averaging

To decrease Poissonian noise in the data, neutron count rates can be averaged over a longer time period, increasing the absolute number of counts in the corresponding time window, w (e.g., $w = 3$ if an hourly time series is averaged over 3 hours). This will reduce the uncertainty band, $\sigma_{\tilde{N}'}$, around each averaged neutron value, \tilde{N}' , according to [Schrön et al., 2018], Eq. 5:

$$\sigma_{\tilde{N}'} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{w}} \sigma_{N'} . \quad (15)$$

⚠ As by definition, the reduction of the Gaussian standard deviation by averaging requires the data values to be Gaussian distributed. I.e., averaging of the time series should be done on data that is largely free of non-Gaussian, i.e., systematic influences. This is why smoothing or aggregation of data must be performed *after* the above corrections. Moreover, it must be done *before* the conversion to soil moisture, as the $\theta(N)$ relationship is non-linear, which will substantially skew the Gaussian-distribution.

If neutron counts are averaged by smoothing or aggregation, the resulting neutron count rate, \tilde{N}' must be again in units of counts per hour (cph).

10.1 Smoothing

Smoothing algorithms typically follow the Savitzky-Golay scheme, which changes each value of the time series based on the value of its neighbors, while preserving the original temporal resolution:

$$\tilde{N}'(t_i) = \frac{1}{w} \sum_{j=i-w_2}^{j=i+w_2} p(t_j) N'(t_j) , \quad (16)$$

where \tilde{N}' is the smoothed corrected neutron count rate, $w = 1 + 2w_2$ is the total time window for averaging and must be an odd number (e.g., 7, 13, 25) in order to include the current value, $N'(t_i)$, together with an equal number of its neighbours, w_2 , before and after the central time t_i . The polynomial $p(t_j)$ gives weight to the neighbours of $N'(t_i)$ and is currently recommended to equal 1, such as the presented procedure becomes equivalent to a simple moving (rolling) mean. It is recommended to use this centralized rolling mean for most cases, and a right-aligned rolling mean for real-time data monitoring.

10.2 Aggregation

The aggregation of the time series changes its temporal resolution, Δt , from, e.g., from 1 hour to 1 day. To preserve the units of cph, the aggregated neutron measurements need to be divided by the number of values in this time period, w . Furthermore, a value at time t should represent the average count rate measured between t and $t + \Delta t$:

$$\tilde{N}'(t_j) = \frac{1}{w} \sum_{t_j}^{t_j+\Delta t} N'(t_i) . \quad (17)$$

11 Conversion to soil moisture

11.1 The neutron-to-soil moisture relationship

The general theoretical relationship between neutrons and water is a combination of a hyperbolic and an exponential term. [Köhli et al., 2021] has suggested the following form based on neutron physics simulations:

$$N'(\theta, h) = N_D \left(\frac{p_1 + p_2 \theta}{p_1 + \theta} \cdot (p_3 + p_4 h + p_5 h^2) + e^{-p_6 \theta} (p_7 + p_8 h) \right), \quad (18)$$

where p_i are the numerical parameters "MCNP drf" provided in their table A1, h is the absolute air humidity, $\theta = 1.43 \theta_{\text{grv}}$, and N_D is a scaling parameter which mainly depends on the detector.

To convert corrected neutron count rates, N' (or \tilde{N}' if averaged), to gravimetric water equivalent, θ_{grv} (in g/g), this relationship needs to be inverted numerically, which has been implemented in recent processing codes, such as Nepton.

In the past 15 years, most studies have employed a simplified approximation of this relationship presented by [Desilets et al., 2010], which only considers a hyperbolic term. While it comes with an analytical inverse formulation, it (i) shows significant deviations for very dry conditions, $\theta < 0.10$ g/g, and (ii) separates the influence of air humidity by relying on the correction method suggested in section 8.2. Nevertheless, this approximation has shown sufficient performance for most COSMOS stations under humid climate and is currently recommended for basic COSMOS data processing. The inverse function can be expressed as:

$$\theta_{\text{grv}}(N') \approx \frac{a_0}{N'/N_0 - a_1} - a_2 \equiv p_0 \frac{1 - N'/N'_{\text{max}}}{p_1 - N'/N'_{\text{max}}}. \quad (19)$$

Here, the term on the right-hand side has been suggested by [Köhli et al., 2021] as a less ambiguous formulation with fewer parameters than the formulation from [Desilets et al., 2010]. N'_{max} is the maximum neutron flux under perfectly dry conditions, strictly speaking only reached when no other hydrogen pools are present that reduce the neutron flux (compare Eq. (31)). Its value strongly depends on the individual detector sensitivity. Parameters $p_0 = -a_2$, $p_1 = 0.346$, and $N'_{\text{max}} = 1.0746 \cdot N_0$ can be derived from the parameters used so far in the Desilets equation, where $a_0 = 0.0808$, $a_1 = 0.372$, $a_2 = 0.115$ [Desilets et al., 2010]. The scaling parameter N_0 is site-dependent as it implicitly accounts for uncertainties introduced by site heterogeneity, detector type, unknown hydrogen pools, and by the approximative character of the equation itself.

⚠ Note that other approximations of Eq. (18) exist, which are more accurate than Eq. (19) and have an analytical inverse representation [Köhli, 2025]. They are currently under discussion by the community and may be good candidates for future updates of this section.

11.2 Correction for additional soil hydrogen sources

The gravimetric water equivalent represents all hydrogen sources visible to the neutrons. In order to retrieve only the soil moisture value, it has to be corrected for additional hydrogen pools, such as water equivalent from soil organic matter, θ_{org} (in g/g) or lattice water in clay soil, θ_{latt} (in g/g).

$$\theta'_{\text{grv}}(N') = \theta_{\text{grv}}(N') - \theta_{\text{org}} - \theta_{\text{latt}}. \quad (20)$$

These values could be estimated from local soil samples, literature values, or soil databases like SoilGrids or OpenLandMap-soildb. Water equivalent from soil organic matter can be estimated from soil organic carbon data, C_{org} (in g/g), using the stoichiometric conversion suggested by [Franz et al., 2013]:

$$\theta_{\text{org}} = 0.556 \cdot C_{\text{org}}. \quad (21)$$

Lattice water could be determined from soil clay content, Clay (in g/g), following the empirical approach:

$$\theta_{\text{latt}} = a + b \cdot \text{Clay}, \quad (22)$$

where $a = 0.0149$, $b = 0.16$ determined for american soil [Dong and Ochsner, 2018] or $a = 0$, $b = 0.1783$ determined for australian soil [Greacen et al., 1981].

! In forests there is an additional source of hydrogen, the water in the litter layer. This is difficult to measure as it changes in time, while it is a source of surface water that is well visible by the CRNS. Its proper treatment during data processing is currently under discussion. It is recommended to carefully interpret the resulting soil moisture product from CRNS as a combined value including both, water in the soil and in the litter layer.

11.3 Scaling to volumetric soil moisture

In order to retrieve volumetric soil water content, θ (in m^3/m^3), the value needs to be scaled by soil bulk density, ρ_b (in g/cm^3):

$$\theta(N') = \theta'_{\text{grv}}(N') \cdot \rho_b. \quad (23)$$

12 Soil moisture quality control

To indicate unrealistically high values in the CRNS-derived soil moisture time series, it is recommended to flag values greater than local soil porosity, Φ (in %). Overshoot in CRNS-derived soil moisture above soil porosity could still occur, if additional water was accumulated that has not been accounted for in the previous section, such as ponding water or intercepted water after huge rain events, or snow. These water sources are typically not recognized by in-situ soil moisture probes or infiltration models. Therefore, no general recommendation can be given, and the interpretation and usage of these values should be determined by the specific use case.

Variable	Minimum value	Maximum value
θ	0	Φ

13 Soil moisture uncertainty

The statistical uncertainty of CRNS-derived soil moisture can be calculated on the basis of the corrected neutron count uncertainty, $\sigma_{N'}$. Due to the non-linearity of the neutron-to-soil moisture relationship, the propagated uncertainty is highly asymmetric [Iwema et al., 2021], i.e. the error towards wetter values, σ_{θ}^+ , is typically higher than the error towards dryer values, σ_{θ}^- . The numerically simplest approach is to estimate the impact of neutron uncertainty on the soil moisture uncertainty by the finite distance method:

$$\text{upper error: } \sigma_{\theta}^+ = \theta(N') - \theta(N' - \sigma_{N'}), \quad (24)$$

$$\text{lower error: } \sigma_{\theta}^- = \theta(N') - \theta(N' + \sigma_{N'}). \quad (25)$$

If a single symmetrical uncertainty value is required, the error propagation presented by [Weimar et al., 2020] could be used:

$$\sigma_{\theta} = \left| \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial N'} \sigma_{N'} \right| = (\theta / \rho_b + a_2 + \theta_{\text{org}} + \theta_{\text{latt}})^2 \cdot \frac{\rho_b}{a_0 N_0} \sigma_{N'}. \quad (26)$$

It is important to note that these stochastic uncertainty estimates do not account for other (systematic) uncertainties, e.g., due to unconsidered biomass effects [Avery et al., 2016], calibration errors, and unconsidered variations in incoming neutron flux [Baroni et al., 2018], atmospheric pressure [Gugerli et al., 2019], or air humidity [Iwema et al., 2021].

14 CRNS footprint radius and penetration depth

The footprint radius, R_{86} (in m), is defined as the distance within which 86 % of the measured neutrons first probed the soil. It can be determined numerically by integrating the weighting functions, $W_r(\theta, h)$ as shown in [Köhli et al., 2015]:

$$\int_0^{R_{86}} W_r dr = 0.865 \int_0^{\infty} W_r dr. \quad (27)$$

If this calculation is not feasible, R_{86} can be read out from Tab. 3 as a function of θ and h . This table is valid for standard air pressure and no vegetation. To adapt the values on the local conditions for air pressure P and vegetation height H_{veg} , subsequent rescaling of the values is necessary, following the approach by [Köhli et al., 2015]:

$$R_{86}(\theta, h, P, H_{veg}) = R_{86} \cdot F_p(P) \cdot F_{veg}(H_{veg}, \theta), \quad (28)$$

The corresponding functions and parameters can be found in [Schrön et al., 2017], Appendix A.

! Note that the footprint estimation is based on simulations for homogeneous bare soil terrain. It will be different for more complex terrain, e.g. with strong hydrogen patterns of hydrogen pools above or below the surface.

The measurement depth, D_{86} (in m), is the depth within which 86 % of the neutrons probed the soil. It can be calculated at each time step following [Schrön et al., 2017], Appendix A:

$$D_{86} = \frac{0.01}{\varrho_b} \left(8.321 + 0.14249 (0.96655 + e^{-0.01 r}) \frac{\theta + 20.0}{\theta + 0.0429} \right), \quad (29)$$

where ϱ_b (in g/cm^3) is the average soil bulk density in the upper 25 cm, θ is the derived volumetric soil moisture (in m^3/m^3), and r (in m) is the distance from the CRNS. It is recommend to set $r = 1$ as a proxy for the average measurement depth in the footprint. The formula also includes an additional factor, 0.01, for unit conversion to meters.

! Note that this formula was derived based on simulations for average soil bulk density conditions. It may be wrong for extreme cases of highly porous media or particularly dense soil. The valid range is $1.0 < \varrho_b < 1.8 \text{ g}/\text{cm}^3$.

Table 3: Footprint radius, R_{86} (in m), as a function of volumetric soil moisture, θ (in m^3/m^3) as rows, and air absolute humidity, h (in g/m^3), as columns. The data file is also available from [Schrön et al., 2017].

$\theta \setminus h$	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
0.01	231	229	227	225	223	221	219	217	214	212	210	207	205	202	200	197	195	193	190	188	186	183	181	179	177	175	172	170	168	166
0.02	226	224	222	219	217	214	212	210	207	205	203	201	198	196	194	192	190	188	186	184	181	179	177	175	174	172	170	168	166	164
0.03	229	226	223	220	218	215	212	210	208	205	203	200	198	196	194	192	189	187	185	183	181	179	177	175	173	171	170	168	166	164
0.04	231	228	225	222	220	217	214	212	209	206	204	202	199	197	195	192	190	188	186	184	182	180	178	176	174	172	170	168	167	165
0.05	233	230	227	224	221	218	215	213	210	207	205	203	200	198	195	193	191	189	187	185	182	180	178	177	175	173	171	169	167	165
0.06	233	230	227	224	221	218	216	213	210	208	205	203	200	198	196	193	191	189	187	185	183	181	179	177	175	173	171	169	167	166
0.07	233	229	226	223	221	218	215	212	210	207	205	202	200	197	195	193	191	188	186	184	182	180	178	176	174	172	171	169	167	165
0.08	231	228	225	222	219	217	214	211	209	206	203	201	199	196	194	192	190	187	185	183	181	179	177	175	173	172	170	168	166	164
0.09	229	226	223	220	217	215	212	209	207	204	202	199	197	195	192	190	188	186	184	182	180	178	176	174	172	170	168	167	165	163
0.10	226	223	221	218	215	212	210	207	204	202	200	197	195	193	190	188	186	184	182	180	178	176	174	172	170	168	167	165	163	161
0.11	223	220	218	215	212	209	207	204	202	199	197	195	192	190	188	186	184	181	179	177	175	174	172	170	168	166	164	163	161	159
0.12	220	217	214	212	209	206	204	201	199	196	194	192	190	187	185	183	181	179	177	175	173	171	169	167	166	164	162	160	159	157
0.13	217	214	211	208	206	203	201	198	196	193	191	189	186	184	182	180	178	176	174	172	170	168	167	165	163	161	160	158	156	155
0.14	213	210	207	205	202	200	197	195	192	190	188	185	183	181	179	177	175	173	171	169	167	166	164	162	160	159	157	155	154	152
0.15	209	206	204	201	198	196	194	191	189	187	184	182	180	178	176	174	172	170	168	166	164	163	161	159	157	156	154	153	151	149
0.16	205	202	200	197	195	192	190	188	185	183	181	179	177	175	173	171	169	167	165	163	161	160	158	156	155	153	151	150	148	147
0.17	201	198	196	193	191	189	186	184	182	179	177	175	173	171	169	167	165	164	162	160	158	156	155	153	152	150	148	147	145	144
0.18	197	194	192	189	187	185	182	180	178	176	174	172	170	168	166	164	162	160	158	157	155	153	152	150	149	147	145	144	142	141
0.19	193	190	188	186	183	181	179	176	174	172	170	168	166	164	162	161	159	157	155	154	152	150	149	147	146	144	143	141	140	138
0.20	189	186	184	182	179	177	175	173	171	169	167	165	163	161	159	157	155	154	152	150	149	147	146	144	143	141	140	138	137	135
0.21	185	182	180	178	176	173	171	169	167	165	163	161	159	158	156	154	152	151	149	147	146	144	143	141	140	138	137	135	134	133
0.22	181	179	176	174	172	170	168	166	164	162	160	158	156	154	152	151	149	147	146	144	143	141	140	138	137	135	134	133	131	130
0.23	177	175	172	170	168	166	164	162	160	158	156	154	153	151	149	148	146	144	143	141	140	138	137	135	134	132	131	130	129	127
0.24	173	171	169	167	165	163	161	159	157	155	153	151	149	148	146	144	143	141	140	138	137	135	134	132	131	130	128	127	126	125
0.25	170	167	165	163	161	159	157	155	153	152	150	148	146	145	143	141	140	138	137	135	134	133	131	130	128	127	126	125	123	122
0.26	166	164	162	160	158	156	154	152	150	148	147	145	143	142	140	139	137	136	134	133	131	130	128	127	126	125	123	122	121	120
0.27	163	161	158	156	155	153	151	149	147	145	144	142	140	139	137	136	134	133	131	130	129	127	126	125	123	122	121	120	119	117
0.28	159	157	155	153	151	150	148	146	144	143	141	139	138	136	135	133	132	130	129	127	126	125	124	122	121	120	119	117	116	115
0.29	156	154	152	150	148	147	145	143	141	140	138	137	135	134	132	131	129	128	126	125	124	122	121	120	119	118	116	115	114	113
0.30	153	151	149	148	146	144	142	140	139	137	136	134	133	131	130	128	127	125	124	123	121	120	119	118	117	115	114	113	112	111
0.31	150	149	147	145	143	141	140	138	136	135	133	132	130	129	127	126	125	123	122	121	119	118	117	116	115	113	112	111	110	109
0.32	148	146	144	142	141	139	137	136	134	132	131	129	128	127	125	124	122	121	120	119	117	116	115	114	113	111	110	109	108	107
0.33	145	143	142	140	138	137	135	133	132	130	129	127	126	124	123	122	120	119	118	117	115	114	113	112	111	110	109	108	107	105
0.34	143	141	139	138	136	134	133	131	130	128	127	125	124	123	121	120	119	117	116	115	114	112	111	110	109	108	107	106	105	104
0.35	141	139	137	136	134	132	131	129	128	126	125	123	122	121	119	118	117	116	114	113	112	111	110	109	108	106	105	104	103	102
0.36	139	137	135	134	132	131	129	127	126	125	123	122	120	119	118	116	115	114	113	112	110	109	108	107	106	105	104	103	102	101
0.37	137	135	134	132	130	129	127	126	124	123	122	120	119	118	116	115	114	113	111	110	109	108	107	106	105	104	103	102	101	100
0.38	136	134	132	131	129	127	126	124	123	122	120	119	117	116	115	114	112	111	110	109	108	107	106	105	104	102	101	100	100	99
0.39	134	132	131	129	128	126	124	123	122	120	119	117	116	115	114	112	111	110	109	108	107	106	104	103	102	101	100	99	98	97
0.40	133	131	129	128	126	125	123	122	120	119	118	116	115	114	113	111	110	109	108	107	106	104	103	102	101	100	99	98	97	97
0.41	132	130	128	127	125	124	122	121	119	118	117	115	114	113	112	110	109	108	107	106	105	104	102	101	100	99	98	97	96	96
0.42	131	129	127	126	124	123	121	120	118	117	116	114	113	112	111	109	108	107	106	105	104	103	102	101	100	99	98	97	96	95
0.43	130	128	127	125	123	122	120	119	118	116	115	114	112	111	110	109	108	106	105	104	103	102	101	100	99	98	97	96	95	94
0.44	129	127	126	124	123	121	120	118	117	116	114	113	112	110	109	108	107	106	105	104	102	101	100	99	98	97	96	95	94	94
0.45	129	127	125	124	122	121	119	118	116	115	114	112	111	110	109	108	106	105	104	103	102	101	100	99	98	97	96	95	94	93
0.46	128	127	125	123	122	120	119	117	116	115	113	112	111	110	108	107	106	105	104	103	101	100	99	98	97	96	95	94	94	93
0.47	128	126	125	123	122	120	119	117	116	114	113	112	110	109	108	107	106	104	103	102	101	100	99	98	97	96	95	94	93	92
0.48	128	126	124	123	121</																									

15 Sensor calibration using in-situ soil moisture

The calibration parameter N_0 (or N'_{\max}) in Eq. (19) can be determined by independent measurements of average soil moisture in the CRNS footprint, θ_{cal} (in m^3/m^3):

$$N'_{\max} = 1.0746 N_0 = N' \frac{p_0 - \theta_{\text{grv,cal}}}{p_0 - p_1 \theta_{\text{grv,cal}}} \quad (30)$$

$$\text{where } \theta_{\text{grv,cal}} = \theta_{\text{cal}}/\rho_b + \theta_{\text{org}} + \theta_{\text{latt}} + \theta_{\text{litt}}. \quad (31)$$

Here, it is important to note that the values measured by in-situ probes is volumetric soil moisture, so that it needs to be converted to gravimetric soil moisture and added on top of the other hydrogen pools in the footprint. If multiple calibration campaigns have been conducted, the final N'_{\max} is the average of the individual values or the optimal value that minimizes the RMSE to every sampling campaign.

θ_{cal} could be determined either by manual soil sampling, or by using a distributed network of soil moisture sensors (TDR or TDT). Both types of data need to be weighted horizontally and vertically to account for the spatial sensitivity of neutron measurement. The horizontal weighting function W_r and the vertical weighting function W_d depend on soil moisture and air humidity at the day of interest, and can be calculated using the functions provided by [Schrön et al., 2017], Eqs. 4 and 6.

⚠ Make sure that the neutron detector is operating properly during the soil sampling campaign, and that no significant changes of soil moisture occur during the averaging period of CRNS (e.g., 24 hours) on the calibration time, e.g. due to precipitation, or irrigation. This will reduce calibration uncertainty and eventually the uncertainty on θ .

15.1 Vertical averaging of in-situ probes

For each location/profile in the footprint area, a vertically averaged value of soil moisture, θ_{profile} (in m^3/m^3) needs to be determined. According to [Schrön et al., 2017], this requires knowledge of the weight w_d for each in-situ soil moisture measurement, θ_d (in m^3/m^3) at depth d :

$$\theta_{\text{profile}} = \frac{\sum \theta_d w_d}{\sum w_d}. \quad (32)$$

It is recommended to take at least 3 measurements per profile: one below the surface, 0-10 cm, one at 10-20 cm, and one at 20-30 cm. Since typically there are very few in-situ measurements available per profile, while the depth-sensitivity of the neutrons is highly non-linear, it is recommended to integrate over the whole profile up to 1 m and define ranges within which each measurement is representative:

$$w_d = \int_{d_i}^{d_j} W_d dd \propto W_{d_i} - W_{d_j}. \quad (33)$$

Here, the weight of an in-situ measurement at depth d is given by integrating the weighting function W_d from an upper depth, d_i to a lower depth, d_j . For the uppermost measurement, $d_i = 0$ (the surface) and d_j would be the half-way distance to the next measurement below that sensor. For the lowest measurement, $d_j = 1$ (1 m depth). Since W_d has an exponential form, the integration is trivial and simply the difference between the values of W_d at d_i and d_j .

15.2 Horizontal averaging of profile values

It is recommended to take sufficient in situ soil moisture samples such that the soil moisture in the CRNS footprint area is covered representatively, while the locations can be picked depending on local spatial heterogeneity and the resources available. The calibration samples need to be averaged using the horizontal weighting function W_r according to [Schrön et al., 2017], section 4.5. For this,

Figure 2: Screenshot from the tool <https://neptoon-tools.streamlit.app> where a sampling scheme could be designed based on areas of equal contribution (color shades) depending on wetness conditions (slider) and on the desired number of annuli, e.g., 2 (blue), 3 (green), or 5 (brown).

regions (annuli) of equal contribution (e.g., 5 annuli of 20% quantiles) to the neutron signal could be defined depending on the local conditions (i.e., atmospheric pressure, air humidity, average soil moisture) that influence the spatial sensitivity of the CRNS. All sampling points that fall within an annulus A are arithmetically averaged and therefore receive the same weights, which are calculated according to the weighting scheme of [Schrön et al., 2017]. More specifically, W_r is integrated throughout the domain to find the radii r_1 and r_2 that define the five annuli $A(r_1, r_2)$ within which all samples are equally averaged:

$$\theta_{\text{cal}} = \frac{1}{5} \sum_{A=1}^5 \theta_A, \quad \text{where } \theta_A = \langle \theta_r \rangle \quad \forall r \in (r_1, r_2) \quad (34)$$

$$\text{with } \int_{r_1}^{r_2} W_r dr = \frac{A}{5} \int_0^{\infty} W_r dr. \quad (35)$$

In particular, this method ensures that soil samples taken using the outdated COSMOS scheme (25, 75, 200) m, which assumed larger CRNS footprints, are not double weighted. Due to the long distances of this COSMOS sampling scheme, there may be no soil samples in one annulus. If this is the case (e.g., using historical soil sampling data), the samples in the next larger ring may receive double the weight. For instance, the soil samples taken at 25 m distance are also representative for the soil moisture in the first annulus around the sensor.

For calibration campaigns, it is recommended to follow this approach, i.e., to find the distances r_i that define the five annuli and to take an equal number of soil samples in each annulus around the sensor. To determine these annuli, online tools could be used as a guideline, such as <https://neptoon-tools.streamlit.app> (see also Fig. 2). It is generally recommended that each land use class in the footprint should be equally represented, and that small irregular features should generally be avoided, such as tractor lines.

16 Conversion to snow water equivalent

Conversion to snow products will be considered for future versions of this document.

17 Processed data requirements

The minimum requirements for processed CRNS data should include the following columns:

Variable	Units	Symbol
Date and time	UTC	t
Neutron counts	cph	N
Corrected neutron counts	cph	N'
Corrected neutron uncertainty	cph	$\sigma_{N'}$
Air pressure	hPa or mbar	P
Air absolute humidity	g/m^3	h
Volumetric soil moisture	m^3/m^3	θ
Vol. soil moisture lower uncertainty	m^3/m^3	σ_{θ}^-
Vol. soil moisture upper uncertainty	m^3/m^3	σ_{θ}^+
Vol. soil moisture symm. uncertainty	m^3/m^3	σ_{θ}
Footprint radius	m	R_{86}
Measurement depth	m	D_{86}

Meta data should include the following parameters that are specific to the site, required to reprocess the data, and typically constant in time:

Variable	Units	Symbol
Original time resolution	sec	Δt
Latitude, Longitude	decimal degree	lat, lon
Cutoff rigidity	GV	R
Atmospheric depth	g/cm^2	x
Barometric coefficient	mbar^{-1}	β
Neutron monitor station	name	NM
Reference air pressure	hPa or mbar	P_{ref}
Reference air humidity	g/m^3	h_{ref}
Reference neutron monitor counts	cps	M_{ref}
Calibration date time	UTC	t_{cal}
Calibration wt. avg. soil moisture	g/g	θ_{cal}
Calibration parameter	cph	N_0
Calibration parameter	cph	N_{max}
Aggregation window	hours	Δt_{agg}
Smoothing window	hours	w
Soil (dry) bulk density	g/cm^3	ρ_{b}
Soil porosity	%	Φ
Lattice water	g/g	θ_{latt}
Organic water equivalent	g/g	θ_{org}
Dry aboveground biomass	kg/m^2	B

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